

Evolving (Im)Mobility Regimes: Migrant Workers' Entitlement and Precarization in Times of Crisis

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In this political-social-legal study, we seek to analyze the link between 'crises,' the legal changes that often accompany them, and forms and processes of precarization. We will analyze this interrelation by focusing on the situation and the entitlements of migrant workers. The study is based on a multilevel design and entails two sub-projects, each of which with a different methodological and temporal focus.

The first subproject investigates, on a macro level, the legal, macroeconomic, and socio-demographic constellations that lead to a distinct increase in precarity. This is done by working out legal and policy changes in several in-depth case studies referring to three European countries, and by carrying

out statistical analyses of existing EU/EFTA datasets dealing with the labor market situation and living conditions.

In the second subproject, we focus on the time during and after the Covid-19 pandemic, analyzing the link of 'crises measures' to the mechanisms of precarization on a meso/micro level and integrating the individual experiences and strategies of migrant workers in our analysis. The findings in both subprojects will be integrated to get a deeper understanding of precarization processes as they evolve in the interplay of legal regulations, practices of organizational actors, and the strategies of (im)migrant workers.